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Hybrid Free-Space Optical / cmWave Transmission over Shared Antenna Aperture

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Abstract—Hybrid signal transmission over both free-space optics (FSO) and radio-frequency (RF) carriers can highly benefit from compact air interfaces when adopting shared-aperture antenna concepts. Towards that, we evaluated lensed horn antennas as consolidated air interface compatible with FSO and FR3-band transmission. To simplify the remote radio head further, the joint air interface is paired with mode-selective signal coding and optical modulation to yield noise-robust radio signal transmission in the FSO mode while reaping the benefits of photonic up-conversion to the FR3 band in the RF mode. Evaluation of the hybrid FSO/FR3 transmission over shared antenna aperture yields error vector magnitudes of 5.9% and 9.4% for radio signal transmission in FSO and FR3-band modes over an end-to-end link configuration that involves a fronthauled remote radio head with a compatible optical budget of up to 19 dB, a wireless trunk link for signal relay to a distribution node and local wireless access.

Index Terms—Horn antennas, Free-space optical communication, Sigma-delta modulation, Optical signal detection

I. INTRODUCTION

FREE-SPACE optics (FSO) is an integral part of 6G architectures [1]. Its fiber-grade transmission capacity up to the Tb/s range makes it an attractive solution in support of aggregated access bandwidths – even in fiber-starved environments. However, propagation over an FSO channel is strongly impacted by atmospheric conditions. While turbulence-induced beam wander and spread can be mitigated to some degree by means of beamforming [2, 3] or large-core optics [4], the strong power fading of 50+ dB/km due to dense fog [5] or beam blocking caused by snow can severely impact communication capabilities. In the case of insufficient power margins, these effects can prevent FSO communications even over a short link reach such as it is common for urban microcell scenarios [6] that involve fiber-wireless architectures with fronthaul, wireless relay and distribution segments (Fig. 1). Although signal conversion to a mid-infrared waveband [7] can deliver a solution to this

Fig. 1. Shared-aperture air interface within a fiber-wireless link involving fronthaul, relay and distribution segments.

practical challenge, the typically much simpler pairing of FSO and radio frequency (RF) signals over the same free-space link renders this hybrid transmission scheme as the more compelling approach to prevent channel outage [8]. Towards that, the weather-tolerance of sub-THz or mm-wave frequencies has been proven through earlier works [9-13]. Further simplification of the hybrid communication system would then call for a compact and consolidated air interface. The concept of sharing an antenna aperture through integrating two physical antennas for FSO- and RF-based communications into a single one has been investigated in a few works (Table I), exploiting dichroic THz/FSO filters for the purpose of multiplexing [14] or partially transparent up-conversion photodiodes [15]. While the first approach builds on frequency duplexing for decoupling the air interfaces devoted to the RF and FSO sub-systems, to eventually allow for independent hardware implementations that do not require a co-design, the latter work elegantly introduces a component-centric approach to provide a dual-function RF/FSO air interface – yet introducing optical losses as large as 18 dB at the FSO branch of the air interface [15].

In this work, we extend our initial investigation on lensed waveguide horn antennas as a joint air interface with shared aperture for hybrid FSO/RF transmission [16]. The proposed air interface features a low-loss FSO interface and does not introduce design constraints for the RF and FSO sub-systems feeding the antenna aperture, which can be implemented with a more compact form-factor when compared to frequency-duplexed RF/FSO systems. We specifically aim at the upper mid-band to support RF communications in the FR3 range – the centimeter region in the electro-magnetic spectrum that strikes a balance between beneficial propagation characteristics and bandwidth availability [17]. By choosing this frequency band, we can further capitalize on mature and cost-effective photonic and RF componentry while being able to support bandwidth-conscious end-to-end analogue radio-over-fiber fronthauling and over-the-air (OTA) relay. The performance and modal choice for hybrid FSO/FR3

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TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL DEMONSTRATIONS OF HYBRID RF/FSO SYSTEMS WITH SHARED AIR INTERFACE

Ref.	Adopted technique for sharing the air interface	FSO Wavelength	RF Frequency	Air interface	Form-factor of antenna aperture	Technological challenges
[14]	frequency duplexing through dichroic filter	C-band: 1552.4 nm	THz band: 300 GHz	dielectric plate as duplexer to provide a 90° separation of FSO/RF branches, holding (i) a gradient-index lens, and (ii) a photoreceiver with THz lens	independent RF/FSO air interfaces channelized into a shared aperture	compact form-factor due to dedicated FSO and RF arms, each with individual beam collimation components
[15]	partially transparent photoreceiver up-converter	C-band: 1546.45 nm, 1550.26 nm	FR2 band: 32.5 GHz	uni-travelling carrier photodiode RF / waveguide output with optical lens	identical RF/FSO aperture: packaged photodiode with optical lens	co-design, trade-off with optical pass-through loss (18 dB)
<i>this work</i>	lensed horn antenna integrating RF and FSO feeds	C-band: 1546.45 nm	FR3 band: 16.5 GHz	WR-51 waveguide horn antenna (15 dBi) with 3" lens optics	identical RF/FSO aperture: 6.5 cm long RF horn, 3" lens diameter	co-design of horn antenna geometry to efficiently support RF and FSO signals

Fig. 3. Path loss for (a) FSO and (b) FR3 out-door link as a function of the visibility, including the weather events of (c) light snowfall and (d) dense fog.

Fig. 2. Path loss measurement for short-reach terrestrial FSO and FR3 out-door link.

transmission will be enabled through choosing noise-robust sigma-delta ($\Sigma\Delta$) modulation of the radio signal, together with mode-selective line coding and modulation in either optical intensity or phase. Towards that, we show dual-mode operation involving digitized radio-over-fiber transport over fiber/FSO and analogue radio-over-fiber transmission over fiber/FR3 while leveraging photonic up-conversion through a simplified coherent fronthaul receiver at the same time.

The manuscript is organized as follows. Chapter II compares the contrast in path loss for hybrid transmission over FSO and in the FR3 band for a short-reach link scenario.

Chapter III presents the concept behind the shared aperture approach for hybrid FSO/RF transmission and characterizes key enabling components. Chapter IV introduces the experimental framework for performance evaluation, while Chapter V investigates the process of photonic up-conversion in the RF transmission mode. Chapter VI then elaborates on the end-to-end transmission performance of the radio signal using FSO and RF modes. Chapter VII provides an investigation towards fading-free operation in view of the inevitable polarization transform along the fiber-furnished fronthaul span. Finally, Chapter VIII concludes the findings.

II. SHORT-REACH LINK PATH LOSS UNDER POOR WEATHER

In order to assess the impact of unfavorable weather conditions on short-reach terrestrial links, the path loss of both, FSO and RF-based transmission in the FR3 band have been characterized. For this purpose, two parallel point-to-point links dedicated to FSO and FR3 transmission were spanned over a roof-top, each of them featuring a link reach of 63 m. These links, whose setup is presented in Fig. 2, are fed through single-mode fiber (SMF) feeders to acquire (i) the transmission loss of the FSO link through optical power monitoring, and (ii) the RF channel response through vector network analysis (VNA). For the latter, high-bandwidth (30.4 GHz) Mach-Zehnder modulators (MZM) and broadband PIN photodiodes (29.9 GHz), whose electro-optic bandwidth characteristics exceed that of the FR3 frequency range (7.125–

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Fig. 4. Shared horn-antenna aperture and modulation switching between intensity- and phase-modulated NRZ-/RZ-coded $\Sigma\Delta$ signal feed to support FSO or photonic up-converted FR3 transmission, respectively.

24.25 GHz), have been employed as opto-electronic converters within the roof-top feeders. While the permanently installed FSO terminals are purely passive and merely include collimation optics, the FR3 installations that included active lab equipment within a waterproof case have been placed temporarily at the out-door environment to capture severe weather events. Moreover, the meteorological visibility has been continuously logged during channel measurements using a visibility meter.

The impact on the FSO and FR3 path loss due to reduced visibility is reported in Fig. 3. Measurement data has been obtained during winter 2024 and autumn 2025, during which the visibility has been fallen below 1 km for 13.1% of the measurements, including heavy fog with a visibility down to 183 m. For the FSO channel, data has been acquired over 22.5 days, while due to the temporary installation of the FR3 link the data resorts to 4.1 days during which fog events and snowfall had been occurring.

For FSO transmission at 1550 nm, for which results are shown in Fig. 3(a), we see a rapid increase in path loss once the visibility drops below 600 m. A strong signal fading of up to 36.2 dB applies for the lowest visibility of 183 m (Fig. 3(d)), despite the short link reach. This contrast in optical path loss complicates the practical deployment of FSO links. Being further emphasized through square-law photodetection, the high dynamic loss range would not only require adaptive gain control but also a high optical launch power to sustain high-rate data transmission in combination with a reasonable receiver complexity.

The path loss conditions in the FR3 band at 16.5 GHz, which are reported in Fig. 3(b), become more favorable. Despite the poor visibility below 200 m, the path loss remains less than 5 dB. This low loss value is also a consequence of the short-reach nature of the link, for which beam divergence does not yet impact the RF path loss significantly. As a result, signal transmission can be maintained without adaptation of the transmission system – in stark contrast to the FSO link.

Fig. 5. RF characteristics when adopting a shared-aperture antenna configuration for (a) WR-51 and (b) WR-34 and WR-28 waveguides. (c) Deviation in response due to accommodation of fiber-optics (WR-34, WR-28) and lenses (WR-51). (d) In-band peak-to-peak ripple in the WR-51 band when considering a signal bandwidth of 250 MHz.

However, we noticed that the low-loss channel conditions did not recover once the fog clears and visibility is recovered. This artifact is explained by the temperature drop beneath 0°C , which caused humidity on the shielding case of the FR3 terminal to freeze. This gradual build-up of ice resulted in an extra loss penalty of ~ 3 dB for the end-to-end response. Yet, the overall link loss remained lower than 10 dB, evidencing the FR3 band as an attractive alternative to facilitate signal transmission in the low-visibility regime. The measurement data for the FR3 link further includes light snowfall (Fig. 3(c)), which leads to short-lived beam blocking for FSO transmission. In the FR3 band, this snow event merely led to a spread of 1.3 dB in RF channel transmission.

Even though the atmospheric conditions that were faced during the measurement period do not holistically cover the breadth of unfavorable weather events, it captures a very characteristic event where FSO systems are severely impacted.

III. AIR INTERFACE WITH SHARED ANTENNA APERTURE

A. Wireless FSO/FR3 Relay with Shared Aperture

A way to reduce the form-factor of the antenna while providing resiliency to weather can be found in shared antenna apertures, which enable both, RF- and FSO-based data transmission. The approach for such hybrid FSO/RF transmission adopted in the present experiment is introduced

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Fig. 6. Experimental setup to evaluate fronthauled radio-over-fiber transport towards a RRH, which facilitates an over-the-air radio relay to a REL node by means of hybrid FSO/FR3 transmission that involves a shared-aperture air interface, before further wireless distribution of the radio signal towards the TET. The inset ζ shows the optical spectrum at the fronthaul link when additionally transporting a RF-LO for the photonic up-conversion at the REL node.

in Fig. 4. For the purpose of radio signal transmission, an orthogonally frequency division multiplexed (OFDM) radio signal is transmitted on its intermediate frequency (IF) at f_{OFDM} as a $\Sigma\Delta$ -coded binary signal [18]. The use of a digitized radio-over-fiber transport over the optical fronthaul link allows the use of simple and cost-effective two-level transmitters [19]. Specifically, non-return-to-zero (NRZ) intensity modulation (IM) can be used to encode the $\Sigma\Delta$ signal for FSO transmission, after which direct photodetection is employed to yield the electrical representation of the radio signal that has been optically transported over fiber and air. This choice for NRZ-IM is primarily motivated by its simplicity when implementing optical signal modulation and detection.

On the other hand, the alternative RF-based OTA transmission mode for hybrid RF/FSO transmission can build on photonic up-conversion. To accomplish this frequency conversion, a local oscillator (LO) of a coherent receiver that feeds the RF link is optically synchronized with a spectral harmonic of the $\Sigma\Delta$ signal. Such a harmonic is yielded by encoding the digitized radio signal in a return-to-zero (RZ) format, which as a self-clocking format introduces a spectral harmonic to the signal spectrum. Together with the oversampling inherent to $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation, this choice enforces a harmonic that is spaced by ν_{RZ} from the optical carrier Λ . For the specific example presented in Fig. 4, an FR3-band carrier frequency of $\nu_{\text{FR3}} = 16.5$ GHz is obtained by choosing $\nu_{\text{RZ}} = 15.5$ GHz and $f_{\text{OFDM}} = 1$ GHz. Moreover, a choice towards phase modulation (PM) rather than IM for optical transport along the fronthaul can further improve the sensitivity during coherent reception at the antenna site due to the better noise immunity of PM [20].

The operational switch between FSO- and RF-based OTA modes can be simply made by choosing the bias, drive and line code during optical modulation at the centralized radio signal transmitter. Antenna-wise, a waveguide horn is proposed as joint air interface for FSO and FR3-band transmission. The RF signal is injected at the feed section through a coax-to-waveguide adapter, as it is commonly employed. However, this feed section further includes a fiber interface whose optical axis is aligned with the waveguide of the RF feeder. A lens at the output of the horn antenna that is mounted on the feeder then completes the shared-aperture

TABLE II
EVALUATION SCENARIOS FOR FSO AND FR3 MODES.

Scenario	CO	FH	RRH	OTA-R	REL	OTA-D	TET
1	NRZ-IM	0 m	PIN + RX				
2	NRZ-IM	0 m			PIN + RF-LO	FR3	down-conv + RX
3	NRZ-IM	0 m			PIN + LO @ λ_{FR3}	FR3	down-conv + RX
4	NRZ-IM	8.6 km			PIN + LO @ λ_{FR3}	FR3	down-conv + RX
5	NRZ-IM	8.6 km	lensed horn	FSO	PIN + LO @ λ_{FR3}	FR3	down-conv + RX
6	RZ-PM	0 m	EML				
7	RZ-PM	8.6 km	EML				
8	RZ-PM	8.6 km	EML + lensed horn	FR3	down-conv + RX		
9	RZ-PM	8.6 km	EML + lens-less horn	FR3	down-conv + RX		
10	RZ-IM	8.6 km	EML + lensed horn	FR3	down-conv + RX		
11	NRZ-IM	8.6 km	EML + lensed horn	FR3	down-conv + RX		
12	RZ-PM	8.6 km	EML + lensed horn	FR3	PA	FR3	down-conv + RX

installation. Given the SMF launch with its numeric aperture (NA) of 0.14, there is no optical truncation due to the boundaries of the RF waveguide. While its air-filled cross-section of 13×6.5 mm² for a WR-51 design is wide enough, the length of 6.5 cm for a horn antenna to accomplish a gain of 15 dBi is compatible with reasonable focal lengths such as $f = 85$ mm for 2" or 3" lens optics, as required to collimate the FSO beam.

B. RF Characteristics of the Shared-Aperture Air Interface

The impact of a shared antenna aperture on the RF propagation characteristics along feed waveguides and horn antennas is characterized in Fig. 5(a) for the waveguide standard WR-51 (15–22 GHz). Measurement data is provided for a complete OTA configuration where both air interfaces include horn antennas and optical lenses. Here, a faint ripple appears for the lensed configuration, which suggests feedback of the optics on the RF channel, as evidenced by the slightly increased S11 response of the lensed aperture.

Moreover, back-to-back S21 and S11 characteristics have been acquired for WR-34 (22–33 GHz) and WR-28 (26.5–40 GHz) waveguides in view of migrating the concept to mm-

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Fig. 7. (a) Optical $\Sigma\Delta$ spectra at the fronthaul, shown for various coding and modulation settings. (b) Received up-converted radio signal after EML-based coherent homodyne detection at the RF branch of the RRH.

wave frequency bands. Towards that, Fig. 5(b) confirms that there is no impact on the smaller RF waveguides due to the insertion of the same SMF port at the coax-waveguide feed adapters.

Figure 5(c) summarizes the deviation from the fiber-less waveguide response over all frequency regions covered by the WR-51, WR-34 and WR-28 adapters, denoted as δ_{S21} . In this back-to-back case without OTA transmission, the ripple in δ_{S21} due to the inclusion of a fiber port remains lower than 0.6 dB. In the case of additionally furnishing the shared-aperture antenna with lens optics, as it applies to the WR-51 system, the induced feedback increases δ_{S21} up to 1.9 dB when referenced to the specified WR-51 frequency range. However, we did not observe signs of deep fading.

Even though a deviation exists with respect to the lens-less antenna configuration, the in-band peak-to-peak ripple ρ_{21} for the lensed antenna aperture that affects the signal reception, shown in Fig. 3(d), remains within a range of 1.03 dB when considering a signal bandwidth of 250 MHz – as will be applied later during the evaluation of the transmission performance. This peak-to-peak ripple is comparable to typical RF bandpass filter functions, which have been proven to introduce a small yet tolerable reception penalty [21].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP FOR RADIO ACCESS INVOLVING RELAY & DISTRIBUTION NODES

The experimental setup to evaluate the shared-aperture approach for hybrid FSO/FR3 transmission is depicted in Fig. 6. At the central office (CO), an OFDM radio signal is generated at its IF of $f_{\text{OFDM}} = 1$ GHz. It features 128 sub-carriers over a bandwidth of 250 MHz, which are modulated by 16-point quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM). $\Sigma\Delta$ -

Fig. 8. (a) Up-converted FR3 radio at ν_{FR3} and passband filter function before OTA-R transmission. (b) Down-converted OFDM radio signal received by the TET and corresponding EVM per OFDM sub-carrier.

modulation and oversampling leads to a harmonic at $\nu_{\text{RZ}} = 15.5$ GHz when applying RZ carving. A MZM is then flexibly used as a multi-format transmitter to modulate the $\Sigma\Delta$ signal onto an optical carrier at $\Lambda = 1546.45$ nm through either IM or PM, depending on the chosen mode for the wireless trunk relay. The optical signal is then boosted by an Erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) and launched with a power of 10 dBm from the CO over an 8.6-km long fronthaul (FH) link that is furnished with ITU-T G.652B-compatible SMF. An additional variable optical attenuator (VOA) sets the received optical power (ROP) to the remote radio head (RRH) and thus the optical budget for the fronthaul link. At the RRH, the signal is split to feed its FSO branch and the photonic up-converter of the RF branch. Signal transmission through either FSO or in the FR3 band is then conducted over a first wireless trunk link for the purpose of data relay, denoted as OTA-R. A relay node (REL) then receives the signal and serves its local signal distribution over a second, purely RF-based wireless access link (OTA-D) towards a tail-end radio terminal (TET).

A. FSO Mode for Data Relay

When choosing FSO-based transmission for the OTA-R relay, the $\Sigma\Delta$ signal at the fronthaul is transparently relayed from the CO to the REL node over the fiber-based fronthaul and the WR-51 based air interface at the RRH, which is augmented by a 3" lens ($f = 85$ mm) to complete the shared-aperture antenna. At the REL node, the FSO link is then terminated by a simple PIN/TIA receiver with RF limiter. The IF radio signal is subsequently up-converted to the FR3 carrier frequency of 16.5 GHz using a local RF-LO (f_{up3}). To simplify RF management, we further evaluate the optical relay of this RF-LO on a second fronthaul wavelength λ_{up3} , which is transmitted in parallel to the $\Sigma\Delta$ radio signal (see spectral inset in Fig. 6). Lastly, the radio signal is distributed from the REL node to the TET by using open-boundary double-ridged horn antennas with a gain of 15 dBi each. The radio signal that is received by the TET is then down-converted by a local RF-LO to an IF of 2 GHz and the error vector magnitude (EVM) is assessed after digitization of the OFDM signal by a real-time oscilloscope.

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Fig. 9. EVM performance over FSO-based relay mode according to scenarios ① to ⑤.

B. Upper Mid-Band RF Mode for Data Relay

In case that the RF mode is chosen for the OTA-R relay between RRH and REL, the RRH photonically up-converts the $\Sigma\Delta$ radio through a transistor-outline (TO) packaged electroabsorption-modulated laser (EML) with integrated micro-Peltier. We build on the function of this EML as coherent homodyne receiver – a functionality that has been investigated in two earlier works [22, 23] to which shall be jointly referred to for further details. In this experiment, the EML emission Γ is injection-locked to the RZ harmonic ν_{RZ} , which causes an up-conversion of the OFDM signal at $f_{\text{OFDM}} = -1$ GHz relative to the optical carrier frequency to an FR3-band carrier frequency of 16.5 GHz. We employed manual polarization control (MPC) at the CO since the coherent detection process through the EML is sensitive to polarization. Chapter VII will investigate a simple mitigation method to address polarization-selective fading for coherent fronthaul reception. After signal conditioning by a 50 Ω low-noise amplifier (LNA) following the electroabsorption modulator (EAM) based photodiode of the EML receiver, the up-converted signal is bandpass-filtered (BPF) at its intended FR3 band frequency of 16.5 GHz and electrically boosted before its RF-based relay over OTA-R. At the REL node, the received FR3-band radio signal can be simply re-amplified before its further distribution along the OTA-D link toward the TET. There is no need to provide the RF-LO at $\lambda_{\text{up}3}$ in the RF mode. Signal reception and evaluation at the TET node follows the same methodology as discussed earlier for the FSO mode.

V. PHOTONIC UP-CONVERSION TO THE FR3 BAND

Figure 7(a) presents the optical signal spectra at the fiber fronthaul, together with the emission Γ of the EML. This EML locks on the RZ harmonic ν_{RZ} to optically synchronize its LO to the incident signal while accomplishing photonic up-conversion of the OFDM radio signal that is spectrally allocated adjacent to the optical carrier Λ to the FR3 band frequency $\nu_{\text{FR}3} = 16.5$ GHz. The spectra further indicate an optical carrier suppression of 33.7 dB through optical PM. Moreover, the RZ-induced harmonic ν_{RZ} onto which the EML locks is enhanced by 19.6 dB when compared to NRZ coding.

The electrical signal spectrum received by the EML in the

Fig. 10. EVM performance over RF-based relay mode according to scenarios ⑥ to ⑫.

RF branch of the RRH is reported in Fig. 7(b), whereas a close-up around $\nu_{\text{FR}3}$ is included in Fig. 8(a). The sensitivity gain of optical PM over IM can be clearly seen in the signal spectra. Moreover, the good suppression of Λ due to PM relaxes the filtering requirements (T_{BPF} in Fig. 8(a)) before OTA-R transmission of the FR3 radio signal at $\nu_{\text{FR}3} = 16.5$ GHz. In case that the EML does not fully lock on the incident optical fronthaul signal, a small frequency detuning from $\nu_{\text{FR}3}$ can be noticed. This effect of failing the condition of coherent homodyne detection applies to any incident NRZ-coded $\Sigma\Delta$ signal. Figure 8(a) shows this for the specific case of NRZ-PM modulation. Figure 8(b) reports the down-converted radio signal after OTA-D transmission, which is received by the TET at its IF of 2 GHz. The spectral envelope of the OFDM signal is well preserved and does not show signs of excessive ripple or signal fading.

VI. FSO / FR3-BAND RADIO TRANSMISSION PERFORMANCE

This chapter discusses the transmission performance for OTA relay in both, FSO and RF modes. Results are discussed along the scenarios ① to ⑫, as summarized in Table II.

A. FSO Mode for Data Relay over the Wireless Trunk Link

Figure 9 discusses the EVM performance for FSO-based relay over the OTA-R span as a function of the optical budget (OB) at the fronthaul link. The back-to-back performance for NRZ-IM $\Sigma\Delta$ fronthaul transmission without fiber, up to the point of the RRH (scenario ①), yields a baseline EVM of 2.4% at an OB of 19 dB (\circ). This low EVM can be attributed to the noise-robust digitized $\Sigma\Delta$ transmission over the optical fronthaul link. We then additionally up-converted the IF radio signal to 16.5 GHz through a local synthesizer at the REL node. For this scenario ②, we connected the REL node directly to the RRH node, meaning that there is no air-side OTA-R relay, and subsequently transmitted the up-converted radio signal over the access link OTA-D. In this setting, the EVM degrades by 3.5% at the same OB (\bullet). This is explained by the considerable noise that is incurred for analogue radio transmission over a wireless link. There is no EVM penalty for the same OB when alternatively providing a remote FR3-band RF carrier on a second wavelength over the fronthaul and relay link (\blacktriangle) to facilitate remote RF management (scenario

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Fig. 11. Continuous sweep of light polarization along the fronthaul link over a duration 7.7 hours.

③). Moreover, we do not see an EVM penalty after populating the fronthaul link with transmission fiber (□), as it applies to scenario ④. A dynamic range of 13.6 dB in OB can be supported. This range reduces to 7 dB (■) when feeding the wireless trunk link OTA-R over FSO, using the shared antenna aperture (scenario ⑤) instead of bypassing the OTA-R segment by placing the REL and RRH nodes back-to-back to each other. Despite this impact that arises due to the introduction of additional FSO coupling losses, the accomplished EVM remains similarly low at 5.9% for an optical fronthaul budget as large as 19 dB.

B. RF Mode for Data Relay over the Wireless Trunk Link

Figure 10 presents the radio transmission performance when switching to the RF mode for the data relay of the OTA-R span. When conducting back-to-back transmission over the fronthaul using RZ-PM $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation, the EVM of the signal before OTA-R transmission at the coherent EML receiver output (⑥) indicates that a margin of up to 4.3% towards the 16-QAM EVM limit of 12.5% can be achieved (○). A dynamic range of 12.9 dB can be supported for the optical fronthaul budget. This power range is limited by the emergence of non-linear terms at lower OB values and the inevitable loss of EML locking at the upper OB boundary. We did not see a notable penalty when furnishing the fronthaul with transmission fiber (●, scenario ⑦). When appending the OTA-R span in scenario ⑧ through transmission of the up-converted FR3 radio signal over the shared-aperture antenna configuration (■), we see a reduction in the dynamic range by 1.2 dB towards higher ROP levels. This is attributed to saturation effects arising at the power amplifier driving the wireless link. However, the minimum EVM of 8.5% that is accomplished for OTA-R transmission remains at a similar value. This is also evidenced by the EVM specific to the OFDM sub-carriers, as it is included in Fig. 8(b,◆). Furthermore, there is no significant difference in EVM between the lensed (■, scenario ⑧) and lens-less (□, scenario ⑨) OTA-R links. For the sake of completeness, Fig. 10 includes the EVM for optical RZ-IM signal transmission (▲) according to scenario ⑩. As it can be expected, the optical intensity format is penalized in terms of reception sensitivity –

in particular by 4.7 dB. The dynamic range is nevertheless retained due to a later onset of saturation at higher ROP. On the contrary, an exceedingly high EVM applies to NRZ coding in scenario ⑪. This is because the EML is not able to optically synchronize the photonic up-conversion process for the simple reason that its emission, which yields the LO for coherent reception, remains free-running in absence of a locking harmonic such as it is provided through ν_{RZ} in case of RZ coding (Fig. 7(a)). Finally, RZ-PM transmission over both RF links, OTA-R and OTA-D, leads to a small additional EVM penalty of 0.4 to 0.8 dB (◆). For this end-to-end link configuration in scenario ⑫ that involves the optical fronthaul as well as the wireless relay and distribution of the FR3 radio signal, the margin towards the EVM limit remains 3.2%.

VII. MITIGATION OF POLARISATION-INDUCED SIGNAL FADING

Coherent radio signal reception after fronthaul transmission is subject to polarization-induced power fading. Due to the random polarization transform of the optical signal along the SMF-based transmission link, the incident signal to the EML-based coherent receiver will in general not be perfectly aligned to its optical axis. To tackle the resulting fading in received signal power, a possible strategy for its mitigation shall be discussed in the following.

Polarization diversity schemes are well known in optical communications. Concerning injection-locked sub-systems, earlier works have proposed the use of dual-polarization carriers for data transmission [24, 25] as well as diversity configurations for the locked elements [26]. These approaches enable the polarization-independent operation despite the use of polarization-sensitive opto-electronics. In this work, we alternatively employ a polarization switch (PS) that allows us to introduce a fixed polarization rotation $\Delta\theta$ to alter the state incident to the polarization-sensitive element. In this way, unfavorable transmission conditions that lead to deep fading can be mitigated by recovering power through a simple (binary) switch of the incident polarization state. Even though such a scheme might not lead to optimal performance gains, it is conceptually simple when compared to prior diversity EML configurations [26]. Furthermore, a PS can be realized as a simplified version of a photonic-integrated electro-optic polarization controller, similarly as demonstrated in [27].

To assess the effectiveness of polarization switching, the MPC at the CO has been replaced by an electro-optic PS capable to introduce a polarization rotation of $\Delta\theta = 90^\circ$. An electronic polarization controller (EPC) at the fronthaul emulates a continuous polarization transform along the feeder by slowly sweeping the state of polarization. This sweep is monitored through a polarimeter and is shown in Fig. 11 on the Poincaré sphere. We then acquired the up-converted radio signal spectrum for RZ-PM based $\Sigma\Delta$ transmission with a RF spectrum analyzer and recorded the RF power Ξ of the central OFDM sub-carrier at ν_{FR3} as a figure-of-merit for the robustness of optical signal reception at the fronthaul span.

The evolution of the OFDM signal over a duration of 7.7 hours is reported in Fig. 12, which shows the up-converted

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Fig. 12. RF signal spectra of received and up-converted OFDM signal for (a) single-polarization signal feed over the optical fronthaul and (b) when adopting polarization switching in addition. (c) Evolution of the received signal power for both polarization switching states and for the optimal state of a polarization-switched feed.

Fig. 13. Histograms of normalized received radio signal power Ξ for optical reception with (a) single-polarization feed and (b) when adopting additional polarization switching.

radio signal spectra at 16.5 GHz for (a) signal reception through the polarization-sensitive EML receiver without polarization switching and (b) when adopting polarization switching to mitigate deep fading events associated with the continuously swept incident polarization state. The corresponding evolution of the normalized RF power Ξ of the central OFDM carrier is presented in Fig. 12(c) and is shown for both polarization rotation states of $\Delta\theta = \{0^\circ, 90^\circ\}$. We see several occurrences where the radio signal fades to a degree where it is deemed inapplicable. Some of these fading events feature a loss in RF power of more than 23 dB. However, the deep-fading events for the two rotation states do not correlate in time. When applying polarization switching between the two states to select the optimal, the fading events can be greatly mitigated. As evidenced through Fig. 12(b), only a few fading events with reduced power loss remain for the received OFDM spectrum. These residual events are explained by the sub-optimal rotation angle of $\Delta\theta = 90^\circ$ that is a result of lab inventory limitations, preventing us to include a PS with larger $\Delta\theta$. Nonetheless, the evolution of Ξ quantifies the mitigation in deep fading through a reduction of 9.8 dB. A detailed analysis is provided in Fig. 13, which shows the histogram for Ξ for the implementation without and with PS. In addition to the aforementioned reduction in fading, it becomes evident

that the probability for deeper fading events reduces significantly, as it is indicated by ρ in Fig. 13(b). Further improvement can be expected through an increase in $\Delta\theta$ or through adoption of more sophisticated polarization control mechanisms.

VIII. CONCLUSION

We have experimentally demonstrated the physical integration of a FSO transmission mode in a point-to-point FR3-band RF link by adopting a shared-aperture antenna concept for short-reach urban microcell links. Backed by a $\Sigma\Delta$ representation for the radio signal with mode-specific coding / modulation switching, the digitized fiber-FSO fronthaul towards a signal-distributing RF relay node can be substituted by an analogue FR3-band relay that is assisted by photonic up-conversion to further retain centralized RF management. In this way, a weather-tolerant signal relay is accomplished while the switch between digitized (FSO) and analogue (FR3) radio relay mitigates a potential loss in radio transmission capacity. The EVMs of 5.9% and 9.4% for both transmission modes, which have been accomplished at an OB of 19 dB and for a $\geq 3\%$ margin to the 16-QAM EVM limit, prove this point. A reduction of the EVM in the RF mode is expected for a photonic up-converter that replaces its LNA stage with a noise-optimized coherent EML+TIA photoreceiver. Moreover, its polarization-sensitive nature that leads to power fading upon coherent signal detection can be addressed by adopting a simple polarization switch.

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